

Fundamental Study and Technology Development of the Catalytic Micro-Combustion

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ABSTRACT

Micro-combustion study has flourished over the past decade. Yet, most of the commercial potential of micro-combustion is still to come. Aside from portable electronics, emerging drivers stem from the energy problem of declining fossil fuel reserves and their large environmental footprint upon combustion. The need to capitalize on underutilized energy sources and renewables further stimulate energy research in microsystems. The device miniaturization leads to a large surface area to volume ratio and enhanced heat and mass transfer rates. Both of these effects render homogeneous micro-combustion susceptible to thermal and radical quenching. Catalytic micro-combustion, on the other hand, benefits from enhanced mass transfer but is still subject to heat losses. Indeed, reducing heat losses and proper thermal management within a catalytic micro-burner are of vital importance as is the case for homogeneous micro-burners. Catalytic combustion in micro-burners is reviewed and the role of key operation parameters is elucidated. Results are presented that interpret literature findings.

Keywords: Micro-combustion, Catalytic combustion, Combustion characteristics, Flame stability, Excess enthalpy burners

INTRODUCTION

With growing concerns about declining energy reserves and the environment and a strong desire for lighter and longer lasting electronics, combustion in micro-channels emerges as an important field. Micro-channels are defined as those having a critical dimension (the internal diameter of a cylinder or the distance (gap size) between parallel plates) of 1000 μm or less, which is typically lower than the quenching distance [1]. Meso-scale devices are defined as those whose characteristic dimension is greater than ~ 1 mm. Since these dimensions are greater than the mean free path of molecules under typical experimental conditions, the continuum approximation in both micro-scale and meso-scale devices is still valid [2].

Unlike their conventional-sized counterparts, micro-burners are no longer governed by bulk behavior; rather, gas-surface interactions play a pivotal role. Small scales enable process intensification (e.g., fast heat and mass transfer), higher efficiency, and faster transients (quick startup). The latter aspect is important especially for portable applications where startup and shutdown are common. At the same time, there are challenges in rendering micro-burners operational, including thermal and radical quenching, thermal management, and susceptibility to failure due to thermal stresses. Loss of stability was recognized as early as two centuries ago, when Davy demonstrated that there exists a quenching distance of the order of 1 mm, below which flames cannot propagate through [3]. This principle has formed the foundations of flame traps. In modern devices, one has to combat these challenges to develop robust technologies for various commercial applications [4].

Although the use of catalysis offers versatility to promote chemical reactions in various industrial purposes, catalytic combustion, i.e., catalytic exothermic reaction has not been a majority of them since thermal runaway is hard to control in

ordinary large scale applications. In micro-scale applications, however, this weakness can be turned into one of the significant advantages for sustaining stable exothermic reactions with other advantages, such as immobile heat release zone, no quenching distance, moderate reaction temperature and clean emission. In this paper, catalytic combustion in micro-burners is reviewed and the role of key operation parameters is elucidated. Results are presented that interpret literature findings.

Combustion Characteristics

Fig. 1. Schematic of various processes within a catalytic micro-burner. The mass and thermal processes are shown on left and right ends, respectively, for clarity; these processes indeed take place at the same location in a micro-burner.

Fig. 1 shows the interplay of various processes in a catalytic micro-burner [5]. The bulk flow of reacting gases determines the residence time as well as the energy input into the system. Reactants diffuse from the bulk gas to the washcoat and then inside the porous support (catalyst layer). Reaction takes place on catalyst sites within the support, and products diffuse outwards through the support and eventually to the bulk gas. Since the micro-burner solid structure has a larger conductivity and thermal inertia than the bulk gas, combustion reactions heat up the

walls. Heat is then transferred from the walls to the bulk gas via gas-phase conduction and along the wall via solid-phase conduction. These processes are central to the autothermal operation of a micro-burner. Aside from axial heat conduction, walls are also responsible for heat losses to the surroundings as happens with homogeneous flames. In non-adiabatic channels, heat losses render downstream walls cold, and heat transfer from the hot products to the walls occurs.

The mixing and gas-catalyst contact can be an issue especially for catalytic burners [6]. Enhanced mixing can be achieved with lower pressure drop by introducing static structures (such as an array of staggered “posts”) near the micro-burner inlet. Other alternatives that avoid jetting employ a wire mesh at the inlet [7, 8], a careful design of inlet manifolds [9, 10], or a network of bifurcating channels [11]. These are briefly reviewed in [12].

Fig. 2. Characteristics of catalytic propane combustion computed from CFD simulations in terms of temperature, conversion, and key dimensionless quantities (Nu , Sh and Da) in a Pt-catalyzed micro-burner. For clarity, only the initial 0.5 cm of the reactor is shown in panels (a) and (b). Panel (c) shows the axial profiles of temperature and mass fractions at the wall (symbols) and cup-mixing bulk values (lines). The variations in Nusselt, Sherwood and Damkohler numbers are plotted in the inset panel (d).

Fig. 2 shows CFD simulation results, underscoring characteristics of catalytic combustion of premixed propane/air lean mixtures in a micro-burner of length 1 cm and 600 μm gap. A detailed theoretical analysis is presented in [13]. Unlike homogeneous combustion, where the reaction occurs in a narrow region in the gas-phase, the reaction zone is more spread out in catalytic combustion. Therefore, the maximum temperature is lower, resulting in lower heat loss and smaller temperature gradients in the catalytic micro-burner. The reaction zone spreads over the initial 4 mm of the micro-burner.

As described in [13], an intertwined pre-heating and combustion zone forms (unlike homogeneous combustion where zones are often segregated, especially for low to medium wall conductivities). Near the entrance, the wall temperatures are higher than the gas temperatures due to heat release from catalytic

combustion. Heat transfer takes place from the wall to the bulk gas. Downstream of this region, heat losses from the walls cause a rapid temperature decrease. In this “post-combustion zone,” the direction of heat transfer reverses causing a discontinuity in the Nusselt (Nu) number profile (Fig. 2d). In contrast, the Sherwood (Sh) number profile is monotonic. Both Nu and Sh profiles exhibit an “entrance effect” because of developing thermal and concentration boundary layers [14-16].

Based on the Colburn analogy between heat and mass transfer, the nearly equal values of Schmidt and Prandtl numbers for gases suggest that the Nu and Sh numbers should have similar profiles in catalytic monoliths [14]. However, the heat and mass transfer analogy breaks down in non-adiabatic catalytic microburners due to the changing role of walls from being heat sources near the entrance to being heat sinks downstream. In the pre-heating/combustion zone, the asymptotic Nu_{∞} value tends towards the constant temperature condition of the Graetz problem, while in the post-reaction zone, the asymptotic value equals the constant heat flux value of 4.15. The Sh number profile settles to an asymptotic value of 3.8 (equivalent to the constant temperature asymptote for heat transfer). The Damkohler (Da) number, which is defined as the ratio of diffusion time scale to the intrinsic reaction time scale, for propane combustion varies between 10 and 1 [13]. Thus, propane combustion in catalytic microburner lies between diffusion-limited and reaction-limited regimes, though the rate of reaction is typically faster than that of diffusion. Similar behavior is observed for methane combustion, with methane being more reaction-limited than propane due to being a slower combusting fuel. Hydrogen combustion on Pt, however, is diffusion-limited for typical burner dimensions due to its fast kinetics. The importance of burner dimensions is further discussed below.

Stability of Catalytic Combustion

Fig. 3. Extinction and blowout limits for methane/air combustion in a microburner with thin wall approximation. (note the logarithmic scale of the velocity axis). Both low- and high-velocity limits of flame quenching are predicted when heat losses are accounted.

Maruta et al. [17] were amongst the first to simulate the extinction limits of catalytic micro-burners. They studied the stability of methane/air mixtures in a Pt-catalyzed micro-burner with respect to flow velocity and equivalence ratio. Their results are reproduced in Fig. 3. The region above each curve demarcates compositions for stable methane combustion. The extinction curves have a typical “U” shape, with the two ends representing the low- and high-velocity stability limits. The authors employed the thin wall approximation, which neglects energy dissipation

through the walls. Low flow velocities result in insufficient energy input and low temperatures (due to heat losses) leading to possible extinction. On the other hand, high velocities result in low residence times, whereby the fuel has no sufficient time to react. Under fast flows, blowout may occur. Fig. 3 shows that for adiabatic micro-burners, the low velocity extinction branch disappears. In reality, a low velocity extinction branch is still likely to exist due to finite wall thickness in actual micro-burners (this effect is not captured with the thin wall approximation).

Fig. 4. Attainable regions of homogeneous (hatched region) and catalytic (shaded region) combustion of propane/air mixtures in a microburner of length 1 cm and gap of 600 μm . The maximum heat transfer coefficient is large enough to allow for direct integration with heat needed devices (endothermic reactions, thermoelectrics, etc.). For catalytic combustion, microburners with more conducting walls become more stable at higher velocities (e.g., 2.5 m/s) because greater heat recirculation is required for stabilizing a microburner. Homogeneous combustion is not sustainable at this higher velocity.

Like homogeneous combustion, the stability envelope, in terms of the critical heat loss coefficient vs. wall thermal conductivity, has a typical bell-shaped curve, as shown in Fig. 4. Comparison of stability maps of homogeneous and heterogeneous combustion using a Pt catalyst indicates that catalytic micro-burners have superior stability than homogeneous ones. This is particularly the case at low wall conductivities, where it is especially difficult to stabilize homogeneous combustion. While these are representative results for a specific set of conditions, the enhanced stability of catalytic micro-burners should be a sufficiently general conclusion for effective combustion catalysts. Since the heat transfer coefficients for stable catalytic operation of propane/air mixtures can be in the forced convection regime, harnessing the thermal energy from catalytic combustion using an energy drawing device (e.g., endothermic reaction) directly coupled to a micro-burner is entirely feasible [18-19].

The blowout stability limit is much higher in catalytic combustion than in homogeneous combustion. This can be seen in Fig. 4 at low wall thermal conductivities, when the material conductivity is varied, as well as when the flow velocity varies [20]. As the inlet velocity increases, micro-burners with highly conducting walls tend to become more stable. At these conditions (2.5 m/s and an equivalence ratio of 0.75), gas-phase combustion could not be sustained. The qualitative difference of catalytic micro-burners from homogeneous micro-burners may be attributed to different (flame) stabilization mechanisms. A flame is stabilized within a confined geometry when the laminar burning rate of preheated reactants (due to axial heat conduction) equals the local fuel velocity [21]. In contrast, the reaction zone in catalytic

micro-burners can spread over the entire reactor length, especially at high velocities. The increased heat input at high flow rates compensates for the heat losses even when conversion is incomplete. More conducting walls allow better pre-heating of the incoming gases and move the reaction zone upstream, thus resulting in higher fuel conversion. Fig. 4 indicates that low conductivity wall materials are preferred at lower velocity and thus for lower power output, whereas more conducting walls are optimal at higher velocity and thus for higher power output. While the results are shown only for 2.5 m/s, similar trends are observed at other velocities as well: as the inlet velocity increases, micro-burners with more conducting walls are more stable.

As happens with homogeneous combustion, catalytic burner stability is affected from the fuel choice. Catalytic combustion of methane is difficult to sustain: critical values of heat loss coefficients are low ($\sim 10 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{K}$ or lower) and the inlet feed needs to be preheated to sustain combustion. In contrast, combustion of propane, hydrogen, and methanol on Pt can be sustained in catalytic micro-burners over a range of conditions with much higher heat losses [22]. The fuel specific stability has been attributed to the difference in reaction kinetics and specifically to the activation energy for fuel dissociative adsorption. Hydrogen dissociation is a non-activated reaction. As a result, it has been found experimentally and numerically that catalytic combustion of hydrogen can be sustained at extremely low equivalence ratios. In addition, hydrogen self-ignites on Pt at room temperature (i.e., it does not require external heating). In contrast, methane adsorption on noble metals is activated (an activation energy of $\sim 11 \text{ kcal/mol}$ on Pt) rendering its combustion slow. As a result, heat is not generated fast enough to compensate for heat losses. The activation energy for fuel adsorption drops with increasing paraffin carbon number, and thus, it is fairly easy to stabilize catalytic combustion of heavier alkanes, including logistic fuels, such as JP8.

Radiative Shields and Catalyst Placement

Fig. 5. Quartz heat recirculation reactor (HRR). (a) Catalyst and thermal shields position. (b) Cross-section of the reactor. (c) Flow direction in HRR mode. (d) Schematic of HRR mode: heat flux direction and thermocouple positions.

It is typical in catalytic micro-burners to have a non-catalytic region near the entrance. In vehicular catalytic

converters, blank monoliths are placed at either ends of a catalytic monolith to act as radiation shields and reduce heat loss. It is unclear whether this idea applies to small scales. In recent work, Scarpa et al. [23] reported stability results for various catalyst placements. They fabricated a micro-burner consisting of 5 cm long catalytic (cordierite) monolith and two blank monoliths, each 2.5 cm long, which shown in Fig. 5. The entire assembly was placed in a quartz tube. Their results with three different configurations are reproduced. When the blank monolith placed upstream of the catalytic monolith was removed, the measured temperature decreased slightly, but the extinction limit was not significantly altered. However, when the downstream monolith was removed, the propane conversion decreased and the micro-burner became less stable. A plausible reason is that the downstream monolith provides storage and recycle of thermal energy. This experimental study implies that blank monoliths are not necessary useful for stability.

In order to understand catalyst placement in a single channel, temperature profiles were obtained from 2D CFD simulations for three catalyst placements in Pt-catalyzed propane combustion. The micro-burner length is 2 cm, of which 1 cm only is catalytic. The catalyst is placed in the front, middle, or rear part of the burner. For a fair comparison, radiative heat losses through the side walls are also considered (emissivity is 0.8). We performed natural parameter continuation by varying the coefficient of external heat loss and compared the stability of the three configurations (results not shown). The front configuration is the most stable, whereas the rear configuration is the least stable. Catalyst placement is more important for low conductivity walls where axial heat transfer is slow. At high conductivities, catalyst placement is of secondary importance. It would be interesting to extend these simulation results to different operating conditions in order to generalize our understanding about optimal catalyst placement. Despite differences in geometry and heat storage capacity, these results are in qualitative agreement with the experimental results of [23].

Catalytic Excess Enthalpy Burners

Fig. 6. Various geometries of “excess enthalpy” micro-burners: (a) combustion in counter-current heat exchanger, (b) heat recirculation geometry, (c) serpentine geometry, (d) symmetric heat recirculating geometry, and (e) porous co-current geometry. Shaded regions are solid walls and blank regions are flow channels.

Jones et al. considered various reactor designs to achieve spatial thermal coupling between hot exhaust and cold inlet streams for homogeneous combustion in conventional-sized devices [24]. Interest in excess enthalpy burners has been revived in recent times in order to improve the stability of micro-burners [24]. Various heat recirculating (HR) micro-burner geometries are shown in Fig. 6. Fig. 6a exemplifies the concept of “combustion in heat exchangers,” suggested almost four decades ago in the

eponymous paper [24], while panel b shows a simple recirculating geometry with a single 180° turn. The catalyst may be placed in the inlet channel, the recirculation channel or both channels. Panels (c) and (d) show the serpentine and a symmetric HR geometry, respectively. In both cases, the catalyst may be placed in the central channel so that the flow channels shield the micro-burner walls in the combustion zone. A co-current flow through a porous bed is shown in panel (e), which relies on enhanced mixing in the fluid phase for improved heat recirculation. Heat recuperation is another strategy, where the flow direction is periodically reversed and excess enthalpy is recovered via temporal rather than spatial coupling. The Swiss-Roll micro-burners are also used for extending the stability of catalytic micro-combustion. In Swiss-Roll micro-burners, the catalyst may be placed in the central combustion zone, which is then isolated from low temperature ambient by the heat exchange channels of the Swiss-Roll geometry.

Federici et al. [25] studied experimentally and using CFD simulations the effect of heat recirculation on catalytic combustion in a symmetric geometry and the serpentine geometry. The central combustion zone in these geometries is physically isolated from the ambient by the inlet and/or recirculation zones. They found that the heat recirculation increases micro-burner stability, and the catalytic HR micro-burners are more stable than their homogeneous counterparts. However, both homogeneous and catalytic micro-burners show the same qualitative behavior: the critical heat loss coefficient for micro-burner stability increases significantly in heat recirculating mode as the wall conductivity decreases. For highly conductive walls, HR does not improve stability significantly.

The heat recuperation in reverse-flow combustion and internal heat recirculating reactors have long been studied for elimination of “fugitive emissions” (ultra-lean conditions) [26]. Counter-current reactors and internal heat recirculating reactors are shown to be numerically equivalent to heat recuperating reverse-flow burners under ideal conditions with infinitely fast flow reversal.

In order to understand the role of walls in heat recirculation, the thermal conductivities of the two walls were varied independently in CFD simulations. The flexibility in changing wall materials independently is another advantage of the planar HR geometry. Nine sets of simulations with each possible combination of three wall conductivities (1, 10, and 100 W/m/K) were considered. The most stable system is obtained when both walls have low thermal conductivity due to low heat dissipation and heat losses through the poorly conducting walls. When the inner wall is highly conductive, the HR micro-burner behaves like a straight channel. The change in stability upon varying the inner wall conductivity is much greater than that of the outer wall conductivity, i.e., the inner wall plays a larger role in micro-burner stability.

To understand these results, we performed additional CFD simulations using the reduced expression of propane combustion kinetics on Pt. The CFD simulation results are depicted in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 by simplifying the 3D geometry to the 2D planar geometry. Note that these results are only meant to be qualitative in nature since the planar geometry does not completely capture transverse heat conduction in the monolith. Nonetheless, several observations can be made regarding heat recirculation. Comparison between the centerline temperature profiles of the SC reactor and the HR reactor in Fig. 7c shows that recirculation

preheats the inlet gases before they enter the catalytic monolith. This pre-heating results in superadiabatic temperatures in HR micro-burners. The maximum temperatures in a HR micro-burner are 150-250 K higher than the SC counterparts. The CFD simulations are also capable to qualitatively predict the stability limits (minimum equivalence ratio) of the SC and HR micro-burners (Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Comparison of temperature contours in (a) non-recirculating (NR) straight channel and (b) heat recirculating (HR) geometries; and (c) the centerline temperature profiles for propane catalytic combustion in a monolith reactor. The microburner structure is made of quartz and the monolith (with four 750-micron channels) is made of cordeirite. The figure is scaled by a factor of 5 in the Y-direction for easy viewing. The hatched region in panel (c) is represents the catalytic monolith.

Fig. 8. Maximum temperature vs. equivalence ratio for heat recirculating (HR) and non-recirculating (NR) reactors for propane combustion for the reactor of Fig. 7. Maximum temperature is obtained close to the inlet wall of the central (catalytic) monolith.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper provides a comprehensive overview on recent studies related to fundamental study and technology development of the catalytic micro-combustion. Conclusions and recommendations for future study and some of the key findings are summarized as follows:

- Catalytic combustion has more spread and often overlapping reaction zones due to lower apparent activation energies. The intimate gas-surface coupling leads to a breakdown of the Colburn analogy for heat and mass transfer. Catalytic combustion is superior at these scales over its homogeneous counterpart and can be sustained for fairly large heat losses, much lower wall conductivity materials, and much higher inlet velocities but not necessarily with complete fuel conversion. This enhanced stability and lower operating temperatures enable integration of catalytic micro-burners with energy harnessing devices, such as thermoelectrics and steam reformers, to provide practical devices.
- The fuel choice is important. Fast burning fuels, such as hydrogen and methanol, self-ignite on Pt-based catalysts,

and give very robust operation. Large paraffins give fairly good stability, whereas light hydrocarbons, such as methane, do not. Given the importance of fuel kinetics, one should expect that the catalyst choice (and amount) should also have a profound effect on stability: very active combustion catalysts, such as Pt, should give fast kinetics and best performance, whereas less active catalysts, such as perovskites, should not give as robust performance. Limited experimental data exist to support this hypothesis. Stability enhancement of slow burning fuels can be achieved via adding a highly reactive fuel or using heat recirculation.

- Burner dimensions are important design variables. The gap size affects transverse transport rates of reactants and heat. At low flow rates, where conversion is complete, the gap size is not critical. On the other hand, at high flow rates, smaller gaps increase fuel utilization and device temperatures. The burner length controls the residence time and the available surface area for heat loss. Longer burners are preferred for mid to highly conductive walls and shorter burners give better stability for low to mid conductivity wall materials. Ceramic materials appear to have an optimum length for improved stability. Depending on fuel, combustion in the submillimeter scale can be diffusion-limited, reaction-limited, or in the transition regime. If a single fuel is to be used, one could design the gap size to minimize diffusion limitations without increasing the pressure drop more than needed.
- In practical devices, a pre-heating zone and heat recuperation strategies should be employed. Catalyst placement becomes then important. A limited number of simulations indicate that having the catalyst placed upstream may be beneficial. Further studies are recommended to generalize these findings. As happens with homogeneous combustion, catalytic burner design is a multivariable optimization problem that should be tailored for specific applications.

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